

Ultrasonic investigation of friction processes in granular gouge materials

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ABSTRACT: Understanding the frictional behavior of fault gouge materials has important implications for interpretation of mechanisms involved in fault movements that result in earthquakes. Fault behavior and stability are significantly influenced by properties of the gouge material, especially in old faults. In this study, the main objective is to investigate the relation between changes in ultrasonic wave properties and micro-scale processes that occur during shear failure of gouge materials. We present results from novel ultrasonic wave propagation measurements in which the gouge materials are shearing under constant different values of normal stress in a single direct shear apparatus. Ultrasonic measurements are conducted by a fast data acquisition system and four pairs of shear wave transducers are embedded at the sides of the specimen. The experimental results provide measures of variations in rate and state friction law parameters with changes in the sliding velocity and normal stress as well as changes in ultrasonic wave properties such as the transmitted amplitude and wave velocity. The variations in ultrasonic waves were monitored and compared during both velocity weakening and velocity strengthening phases. Our results indicate that changes in transmitted amplitude are related to changes in contact area between the particles, while the velocity variations are more related to changes in contact stiffness between the particles. Also, the transmitted amplitude and wave velocity variations were observed to be negligible during steady state sliding. With this, during stick slip cycles, the trends were clearly observed to follow the stick-slip behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

Experimental studies have been used extensively to explore influential frictional processes that affect the rock joint sliding behavior (Brace and Byerlee, 1966; Jaeger et al., 2007). In earlier studies, rock joints were assumed to be identical to other materials, such as metals, and follow a general frictional behavior. This assumed behavior is based on two fundamental principles: (a) shear and normal stresses are proportional, (b) shear stress is independent of contact area (Dieterich, 1978). However, parameters such as sliding velocity, changes in sliding velocity, and healing processes can cause significant changes in shear friction of bare rock joints and faults with gouge materials (Rabinowicz, 1958; Stesky, 1974; Wang and Scholz, 1994). Of the various methods available, constitutive friction laws allow for a powerful evaluation of slippage in rock joints and fault gouge materials. The most comprehensive type of laws were developed as the rate and state friction laws with the

following general form (Ruina, 1983; Perrin et al., 1995; Tullis, 1996; Nagata et al., 2012):

$$\mu = \mu_0 + a \ln\left(\frac{V}{V_0}\right) + b \ln\left(\frac{V_0 \theta}{D_c}\right) \quad (1)$$

where μ_0 is the contact friction for steady state sliding at velocity V_0 , V is the frictional slip rate, and θ is the state variable as a function of sliding velocity and contact time. In this formulation, D_c is defined as the required displacement to renew the surface contact. In this framework the contact life time is defined as the ratio of critical displacement to sliding velocity (Marone, 1998).

The terms, a and b , are empirical constants which are determined based on the experimental results. The general form of results obtained by rate and state friction laws is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. General form of rate and state friction laws in two increasing and decreasing velocity steps (Adopted from Scholz, 1998).

In general, a fault's frictional sliding can be divided into two primary modes of "stable sliding" resulting from velocity strengthening and "stick-slip friction" resulting from velocity weakening behavior. Rate and state friction laws use two dimensionless parameters, a and b , to describe the velocity weakening or strengthening of fault gouge and rock joints materials. The frictional stability is a function of a and b parameters such that when $a > b$, the material is velocity strengthening and when $a < b$, the material is velocity weakening. Represented in aseismic movements, the velocity strengthening behavior is always stable since the shear strength increases as the velocity increases. However, in (normal) high frequency earthquakes, the velocity weakening phase makes the system highly prone to becoming unstable and showing stick-slip behavior.

The transition between stable and unstable sliding is controlled by the relation between the stiffness of surrounding rocks and the rheological stiffness of the fault and gouge material (Kaproth and Marone, 2013; Scuderi et al., 2017). The fault zone stiffness is more dependent on the mineralogy, temperature, and the confining stress, while the rheological stiffness is dependent on parameters controlling the true contact area. These parameters include gouge thickness, rock surface geometry and particles shape, in addition to temperature and mineralogy of the particles (Stesky, 1978; Anthony and Marone., 2005; Khademian et al. 2018a,b). The true contact area between the fault plates and gouge material is always smaller than the nominal contact area. The area is a function of stationary contact time, which is usually described with the time related state variable, θ (Bar-Sinai et al., 2013).

A suitable experimental technique for monitoring the changes in contact area and dynamic properties of rock and gouge material is the ultrasonic wave measurement. Active ultrasonic measurements have been identified as a successful method to remotely monitor the changes in mechanical behavior and physical mechanisms occurring

between the tectonic fault plates and gouge material (Hedayat et al., 2014a-d; Gheibi and Hedayat, 2018a). Measured ultrasonic amplitude can provide valuable information into variation of true contact area and subsequently fault weakening mechanisms and its seismic behavior. Variation of seismic wave velocities were also used to monitor the changes in shear and compressional modulus in small strain, however, there are still much ambiguities in understanding the relation between small and large strain stiffness and its evolution in stable and unstable sliding.

In this study, a layer of quartz sand was sheared as a simulated gouge material between two forcing blocks, where each shearing run was held at a constant normal stress of either 15, 20 or 25 MPa. For each normal stress, sliding velocity was varied in multiple steps to investigate the variation of shear strength and friction stability of the gouge material. Parameters of rate and state friction laws were extracted from velocity steps to quantitatively determine the velocity weakening and strengthening regimes as a function of the shearing velocities for the gouge material. Active ultrasonic measurements were simultaneously conducted with four wave transducers to monitor the variation of wave velocity and transmitted amplitude through the gouge layer. The following sections document the experimental procedure and the details of the set up. The findings of this research are also presented in the following sections.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

2.1. Single direct shear device

The photo of single direct shear apparatus used in this study is presented in Figure 2. In this setup, a loading machine and an assembly of transducer holder plates was used. Forcing blocks with an ultrasonic system were utilized on the transducers holder plates to seismically monitor the gouge layer while it was shearing at different shearing velocities.

In this setup, a flat jack connected to an automated servo controlled hydraulic pump was used to apply and keep the desired amount of normal stress on the specimen. Two LVDTs were used to record the changes in thickness of soil specimen during shearing.

Another automated servo controlled hydraulic pump was used to apply the desired amount of shear displacements and various velocity steps. The shear sliding velocities were applied based on the feedback provided by three LVDTs, which were placed 120 degrees apart. The experiments were conducted in the displacement controlled mode and the corresponding shear stress values were recorded through a pressure transducer mounted on the loading frame.

Fig. 2. Single direct shear setup used in this study.

2.2. Ultrasonic imaging system

The ultrasonic waves were recorded by pairs of transducers placed at the two sides of the specimen. As illustrated in Figure 2, the specimen in this setup was placed between two stainless steel plates and two arrays of shear transducers. Stainless steel plates serve as forcing blocks simulating tectonic fault plates. In addition, they transfer the normal stress and shear displacement to the soil specimen and allow for transmitting waves through the gouge layer (Hedayat 2013).

The resolution of recorded ultrasonic waves is controlled by the two factors of (a) coupling material and (b) the contact stress between the transducer's face and forcing block. A thin layer of honey baked at 90 °C for 90 minutes was used as the coupling material between the transducer and forcing blocks. This procedure has been reported in previous studies and resulted in high repeatability and reproducibility of seismic measurements for rock joints (Hedayat et al., 2014a-d; 2018; Shirole et al., 2017) and fault gouges (Gheibi and Hedayat, 2018a). To control the contact stress, a spring washer and number of stainless steel shims with thickness of 0.025 mm were placed underneath each transducer. The spring washers were compressible and deformed as the normal load reached 310 N. This deformation made the transducer the same height as the aluminum cover plate and kept the contact stress constant during the test (for more details of the setup, please refer to Gheibi and Hedayat, 2018a,b).

The main properties of ultrasonic waves recorded in this study include the transmitted wave's amplitude and velocity. These properties vary due to variations in amount of wave attenuation and dispersion resulting from changes in properties of the soil layer. Wave velocity was determined based on the quartz layer thickness and wave

arrival time, which was identified as the first point where the excitation emerges from the background noise (Inci, 2000; Kawaguchi et al. 2001).

In laboratory studies utilizing ultrasonic waves, it is common to explore the changes in the wave attributes. On the other hand, it is less common to explore the absolute values such as absolute transmission and wave velocity values (Hedayat et al., 2012; 2018; Hedayat and Walton, 2017). In this work, the normalized transmitted amplitude values were used instead of absolute value of the maximum transmitted amplitude. The maximum transmitted amplitude was obtained as the peak value in the received signal. Then, these values were normalized with respect to their initial values in each velocity step.

2.3. Tested materials and experimental program

Experiments were conducted on soil specimens composed of pure quartz sand (SiO_2) obtained from US Silica Company, Ottawa Illinois. Ottawa sand was used because it has been used extensively as common standard sand in several studies (Mair et al., 2002; Hong and Marone, 2005; Ikari et al., 2007). The material was named F75 and includes a wide range of particle sizes. The material were first sieved in accordance to ASTM C136 standard and then a uniform fine grained sample with mean particle size of 0.32 mm ($D_{50} = 0.32$ mm) was prepared.

To prepare specimens, soil particles were initially dried in an oven at 95 °C for 24 h. They were then blended with de-aired water and uniformly mixed to achieve a water content of 10%. The moist soil was finally placed in a sealed plastic for 24 hours to reach uniform moisture distribution (Khosravi et al., 2017). The 10% water content was selected experimentally to obtain a uniform and homogenous specimen with repeatable mechanical and ultrasonic behavior (Gheibi and Hedayat, 2018a).

To prepare the specimens, soil particles were distributed in two layers on the square 10 cm by 10 cm grooved stainless steel forcing block. In order to control the density and height of each layer, a leveling lab-jack and four plastic bars were used to adjust the amount of each layer compaction. A cellophane tape around the forcing blocks was used to prevent loss of materials during specimen preparation.

The prepared specimen and transducer holder plates were then placed between the main steel plates where normal stress was applied at the rate of 0.2 MPa/s. After reaching the desired normal stress, shear displacement was applied with a constant rate to the steady state point. Then finally, the different velocity steps were applied.

3. RESULTS

In this study, experiments were carried out to understand the variation of velocity weakening and velocity strengthening trends with sliding velocity. In addition, the link between ultrasonic measurements and the particle

scale processes during shearing was analyzed. In these experiments, gouge layers were sheared at constant normal stresses ranging from 15 to 25 MPa. Multiple velocity steps were conducted to find the variation of rate and state friction law parameters (a and b), as well as characterizing the evolution of gouge stiffness with sliding velocity.

3.1. Velocity strengthening and weakening transition

Figure 3 presents the general shear stress-displacement behavior of three similar gouge layers under different constant normal stresses. In these experiments, a full spectrum of slip behavior from stable sliding to stick-slip behavior is documented. All specimens were initially sheared with the sliding velocity of $5 \mu\text{m/s}$ until the specimens reached the steady state condition. Once steady state was reached, the different velocity steps were applied. In the first step, the sliding velocity was reduced to $1 \mu\text{m/s}$ and then an increasing trend with the sequence of 5, 10, 20, 40, 80 and 130 was followed. As presented in Figure 3, the shear behavior of gouge material does not follow an identical trend in different sliding velocities. For the sliding velocities of 1 and $5 \mu\text{m/s}$, the gouge assembly slips steadily with an equal velocity to the load point velocity. However, as the sliding velocity increases, the gouge assembly becomes more unstable and shows stick-slip behavior. It can be noted that the sliding velocity of the interface is fluctuating between lower and higher values of the load point velocity.

The rate and state friction laws related parameters, a and b , were determined in each individual velocity step for all three specimens. These parameters were determined based on the increase or decrease in coefficient of friction due to the changes in sliding velocities. The methodology for a and b determination is illustrated in Figure 4 for two velocity steps of 5 to $1 \mu\text{m/s}$ and 1 to $5 \mu\text{m/s}$.

Previously, it was assumed that the a and b parameters were independent of sliding velocity. On the other hand, it was assumed that frictional stability of rock and gouge material was dependent on the relationship between rheological and surrounding stiffness, and was also a function of temperature and confining stress (Gu and Wong, 1992; Marone, 1998; Scholz, 1998). However, recently it has been observed that a and b parameters are additionally dependent on the sliding velocity, and one single material may exhibit velocity strengthening or weakening behavior (Kaproth and Marone, 2013; Bar-Sinai et al., 2014). Figure 5 shows the variations in ' a ' and ' b ' parameters as well as the transition between velocity weakening and strengthening behaviors.

Fig. 3. Shear stress-displacement results for three identical specimens sheared at different constant normal stress of 15, 20, and 25 MPa.

Fig. 4. Determination of a and b parameters for two velocity steps under a) 25 MPa, b) 20 MPa, c) 15 MPa normal stress.

The two main mechanisms playing role in frictional behavior of gouge and rock materials are true contact area changes and thermal activation energy. True contact area was observed to reach the maximum value and become saturated at very low sliding velocities. It was also observed that true contact area decreases logarithmically with increasing sliding velocity to reach a minimum value (Bar-Sinai et al., 2014). This reduction in true contact area raises the probability of unstable behavior in the system. However, thermal activation is defined as the required energy for asperities of one side to jump over the other side. This phenomenon varies in an opposite way and actually increases with sliding velocity. With this, the increase in thermal activation energy leads the system toward more stable sliding and velocity strengthening behavior.

For low values of sliding velocity (1 and 5 $\mu\text{m/s}$), all three specimens show a velocity strengthening behavior with positive ($a-b$). In addition, as the velocity increases the ($a-b$) decreases gradually and the system behaves as velocity weakening with negative values of ($a-b$). For low sliding velocities, the dominant mechanism in frictional stability is the change in true contact area, which is a function of confining stress (Majmudar and Behringer, 2005). The absolute values and the relative changes in true contact area is highly dependent on confining stress values. The changes in true contact area increase with normal stress and therefore, as it is observed in Figure 5c, the velocity weakening behavior is more sensible in specimens with higher normal stresses (Bar-Sinai et al., 2014).

Fig. 5. Variations in rate and state law parameters, a) a , b) b and c) $(a-b)$ with sliding velocity for three identical specimens at different normal stresses.

3.2. Stable sliding

In this section, the initial stable sliding and corresponding changes in wave properties for two different normal stress levels are studied to identify the impact of sliding velocity on transmitted amplitude and wave velocity. The gouge

material tested in this study showed stable sliding when sheared at velocities of 1 and 5 $\mu\text{m/s}$. The variation of shear wave velocity, transmitted amplitude, sliding velocity, and changes in large strain shear stiffness are presented in Figure 6 and 7 for the velocity steps of 5 to 1 $\mu\text{m/s}$ at normal stress of 25 and 15 MPa, respectively. The changes in large strain shear stiffness are obtained as the ratio of changes in shear stress to the changes in average shear displacement. Stiffness changes and sliding velocities were calculated based on the recorded data every 0.5 seconds.

As it is presented in Figure 6a, the shear stress drops as the sliding velocity decreases from 5 to 1 $\mu\text{m/s}$. The reduction in sliding velocity increases the average contact time between the particles and subsequently, the inter-particle contact area has more chance to evolve during this extra contact time. With this, the intensity of the ultrasonic waves is controlled by the area of contact because the waves transmit through the inter-particle contacts throughout this area of contact. Therefore, the reduction in sliding velocity and the corresponding increase in the contact area results in an increase in the normalized transmitted amplitude.

Figure 6b shows the variation of shear wave velocity and stiffness changes in a similar velocity step. In this range of velocities, the gouge layer is shearing in the stable phase and changes in large strain shear stiffness of gouge material are almost negligible. This behavior is also elaborated with variation of ($a-b$) in Figure 5c. Correspondingly, the changes in shear wave velocity are negligible and do not follow a specific trend.

Figure 7 shows a similar plot to Figure 6 but for a normal stress of 15 MPa. Comparing the results shown in Figure 6 and 7, the shear stress reduction due to the reduction in sliding velocity is higher in the specimen with 25 MPa normal stress, consistent with results reported in the literature (Anthony and Marone, 2005; Scuderi et al., 2017). Corresponding with changes in shear stress and specimen friction behavior, the changes in transmitted amplitude are more sensible in the specimen with higher normal stress, although both transmitted amplitude and wave velocity follow a similar trend as described before.

Fig. 6. Variations of shear stress and a) normalized transmitted amplitude and sliding velocity b) shear wave velocity and stiffness changes with time in a velocity step from 5 to 1 $\mu\text{m/s}$ under 25 MPa normal stress.

Figure 7. Variations of shear stress and a) normalized transmitted amplitude and sliding velocity b) shear wave velocity and stiffness changes with time in a velocity step from 5 to 1 $\mu\text{m/s}$ under 15 MPa normal stress.

3.3. Stick slip behavior

As shown in Figure 2, the sliding becomes unstable as the sliding velocity exceeds the value of 5 $\mu\text{m/s}$ for the quartz sand. Variation of shear wave amplitude and velocity with a sliding velocity of 40 $\mu\text{m/s}$ under two different normal stresses of 25 and 15 MPa are also recorded and presented in Figure 8 and 9.

The shear slippage in stick-slip cycles can be divided into two main regimes: slow and fast sliding. As shown in Figure 8a and 9a during the slow slippage, sliding velocity is almost two times smaller than the maximum sliding velocity observed in each stick-slip cycle. This slow sliding is coincident with the increase in shear stress, however, the increasing trend in shear stress is very unstable. Once the specimen reaches its maximum shear strength, the sliding velocity increases considerably and the specimen experiences a sudden and fast slip. In contrast to stable sliding, the variation of transmitted amplitude and wave velocity is more considerable and the cyclic impact of stick-slip behavior is clearly observed on the ultrasonic wave properties. As it is observed in Figure 8a and 9a, the transmitted amplitude has an opposite trend with the sliding velocity. In addition, the peak in transmitted amplitude is exactly associated with the minimum in sliding velocities, which is happening during the sticking phase.

The variation of shear wave velocity and changes in shear stiffness are presented in Figure 8b and 9b for normal stresses of 15 and 25 MPa. Changes in stiffness show cyclic variations consistent with stick-slip behavior. The wave velocity variations and changes in stiffness follow a similar trend, in which the maximum in wave velocity corresponds to the maximum value of shear stiffness. However, both shear wave velocity and change in shear stiffness has a phase shift with changes in shear stress. Similar to the stable sliding, the variations in shear stress and shear displacement are more in the specimen with higher normal stress and correspondingly, the variation of shear wave velocity and transmitted amplitude are more considerable in specimens with higher normal stress.

Fig. 8. Variations of shear stress and a) normalized transmitted amplitude and sliding velocity b) shear wave velocity and stiffness changes with time in a velocity step from 20 to 40 $\mu\text{m/s}$ under 25 MPa normal stress.

Figure 9. Variations of shear stress and a) normalized transmitted amplitude and sliding velocity b) shear wave velocity and stiffness changes with time in a velocity step from 20 to 40 $\mu\text{m/s}$ under 15 MPa normal stress.

Traditionally, ultrasonic waves were considered an empirical method to evaluate the small strain shear and compressional stiffness of soil and rock materials. However, extensive efforts have been made recently to broaden the application of ultrasonic waves to understand the frictional processes occurring between tectonic faults and rock joint movements. The findings of this study can bring new ideas in developing methodologies to understand the changes in shear stiffness and contact area of filling materials in rock joints and faults to accurately estimate their frictional behavior. However, more studies on a variety of soil particles under different stress conditions are necessary to be able to further extend the obtained results in this study to the field conditions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a number of shear tests were carried out to investigate the variations of ultrasonic wave properties with different phases in frictional behavior of granular materials. A single direct shear apparatus was equipped with shear wave transducers to monitor the changes in velocity and amplitude of transmitted waves through the soil specimen when different velocity steps were applied to the specimen. The obtained results show different trends for variation of shear stress and frictional behavior of the gouge layer at different sliding velocities. It was observed that sliding velocity had a significant impact on shear strength as well as the frictional behavior of the gouge layer. Depending on the sliding velocity, the gouge material exhibited stable or unstable sliding. In addition to sliding velocity, normal stress showed a significant impact on the stability of the gouge layer where specimens with higher normal stress showed more unstable slip. Ultrasonic measurements were conducted during both stable and unstable shearing and it was observed that changes in transmitted amplitude are attributable to the variation of sliding velocity and the true contact area. The changes in wave velocity were also found to closely follow the changes in large strain stiffness of the gouge layer.

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